

STOMACH PAIN CAUSES, EXAMINATIONS, TREATMENT, RELIEF METHODS

Madaminov Muxammadvali Ikromjon o'g'li

Tashkent Medical Academy

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7295232>

Abstract. *Everyone has experienced stomach pain, because it is not always a sign of the development of a serious pathology. Many people experience unpleasant pain in the stomach due to drinking too much liquid or eating food. But you should know that even a small discomfort can be a symptom of a pathological process that requires urgent help. Therefore, it is necessary to be able to distinguish stomach pain independently and to understand in which cases to consult a doctor immediately.*

Key words: *causes of stomach pain, Tests for stomach pain, Treatment of stomach pain, Stomach pain requiring emergency medical attention.*

ПРИЧИНЫ БОЛИ В ЖЕЛУДКЕ, ОБСЛЕДОВАНИЯ, ЛЕЧЕНИЕ, СПОСОБЫ ОБЛЕГЧЕНИЯ

Аннотация. *С болью в животе сталкивался каждый, ведь не всегда это является признаком развития серьезной патологии. Многие люди испытывают неприятные боли в желудке из-за употребления слишком большого количества жидкости или приема пищи. Но следует знать, что даже небольшой дискомфорт может быть симптомом патологического процесса, требующего неотложной помощи. Поэтому необходимо уметь самостоятельно различать боли в желудке и понимать, в каких случаях следует немедленно обратиться к врачу.*

Ключевые слова: *причины болей в животе, Тесты на боли в животе, Лечение болей в животе, Боли в животе, требующие неотложной медицинской помощи.*

INTRODUCTION

CAUSES OF STOMACH PAIN

The causes of pain in the stomach can be various pathological and physiological conditions. Usually, this syndrome is not permanent, so people ignore it, which is a mistake that leads to the development of serious complications Causes of pathological stomach pain:

Gastritis is inflammation of the mucous membrane of the stomach. The pain syndrome in gastritis is not constant and intense, and is always associated with eating - often unpleasant sensations appear immediately after eating the "wrong" products. will be Note: The acute form of gastritis is characterized by sudden severe pain in the epigastric region, the pain passes quickly, but it can be annoying every time after a meal. If the inflammatory process of the mucous membrane of the stomach is chronic, the patient has a feeling of throbbing pain, abdominal discomfort and pressure expansion.

Dyspepsia (nervous stomach). The pain syndrome in this case has a spastic character, it is accompanied by nausea, feeling of excessive satiety and loss of appetite. Despite the fact that the pain is localized in the anatomical location of the stomach, the "culprit" in dyspepsia is the pancreas, so even the most effective pain reliever with spasmolytic effect does not give the desired effect.

Stomach ulcer. This condition usually develops as a complication of chronic gastritis, so stomach pain is well known to the patient. But when a stomach ulcer appears, the nature of the stomach pain changes — it becomes harder, stronger, and occurs immediately after eating.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Benign tumors, including polyps. It is worth noting that such pathologies do not threaten the life of the patient, but patients experience severe discomfort: when eating (when food enters the stomach, the nerve endings located in the tumor are affected), when they eat a lot. The nature of the pain is non-constant, throbbing, pulling, accompanied by a feeling of fullness in the stomach even when eating a small amount of food. The patient is afraid of stomach ache after eating and is hungry. Medicine also classifies physiological pains in the stomach. They are, of course, caused by the violation of various organs and systems:

Viral diseases, including angina and pneumonia. Usually, in such infectious pathologies, stomach pain is present only in the first three days of the disease, they are accompanied by nausea and diarrhea (diarrhea), the nature of the pain is mild and non-intense. Pathological processes of infectious etiology - in the bladder, pancreas, gall bladder and other organs of the gastrointestinal tract. The patient describes abdominal pain as spastic, not constant. Allergy to certain foods. Stomach pain can appear immediately when the allergen enters the body, and it lasts until the product is digested. The nature of the syndrome is variable - from spasms to almost indistinguishable pains.

Spastic stomach pain is often manifested in stress, nervous tension, and long-term depression. Recently, doctors have been distinguishing a special type - phobic pain in the stomach, which is associated with a feeling of fear, for example, settling in a new job, giving a speech in front of a large audience, etc.

Please note: in general, stomach pain can be caused by any internal disease. But in some cases, it is only a matter of irradiation of the pain syndrome, for example, in gastric myocardial infarction, inflammation of the gallbladder, and even pyelonephritis. Doctors treat pain in the stomach on an empty stomach in the evening as a special point - such pain is caused by the formation of a large amount of hydrochloric acid in an empty stomach. The causes of hunger pain in the stomach are as follows:

The presence of pathogenic bacteria in the organ walls;

The presence of gastrinoma is a benign tumor located at the gate of the stomach, which independently secretes gastric juice with high hydrochloric acid;

Regular violation of the order of eating, eating a lot at night;

Bad-quality tumors that develop gradually - their growth is especially active at night.

RESEARCH RESULTS

EXAMINATIONS CONDUCTED IN STOMACH PAIN

A patient's complaint of stomach pain cannot be the basis for any diagnosis. The doctor should perform a series of tests to determine the true cause of even minor discomfort/pain sensations. Studies on stomach pain include:

Questioning the patient - it specifies the nature of the pain, how often it occurs and its intensity, whether it is related to food and other features of the syndrome;

Ultrasound examination of the stomach and other organs of the gastrointestinal tract allows to identify tumors and pathological changes in tissue structure;

Esogastroduodenography is a unique study of the stomach with a probe and a miniature video camera;

Computed tomography — all pathological changes can be classified and differentiated.

Please note: the patient can monitor his condition to make the diagnosis easier. One week of observations will be enough to fully describe the clinical picture.

What to pay attention to:

Stomach pain most often occurs in the morning on an empty stomach, immediately after a meal or in the evening;

Which products cause discomfort - for example, it can be milk or fatty meat;

Provocative factors - deep breathing, sneezing, pain can significantly increase in an uncomfortable position of the body;

Presence of hyperthermia with pain;

The character of the syndrome is pulling, cutting, tingling, spastic and other types of pain.

DISCUSSION

TREATMENT OF STOMACH PAIN

Spastic pain in the epigastric area can be relieved with antispasmodic drugs, but this will be an emergency. Only a doctor can determine the full course of treatment after examining the patient and identifying the causes of discomfort. Doctors recommend following the following diet for occasional pain in the stomach: Giving preference to lean meat and milk;

Excluding marinated, spicy, sour and salty foods from the menu - they have an irritating effect on the walls of the stomach, and even healthy people can experience short-term spasms; If the feeling of hunger and refusal to eat at night is very strong, then drink a glass of milk with honey.

Severe pain can be relieved with "soft" products, for example, eating pureed soups, steamed meat cutlets, crushed porridges and vegetable purees.

Self-medication is strictly prohibited - the cause of pain syndrome in the epigastric region may be the pathology of a distant organ, which can only be determined by a doctor by conducting instrumental research.

Adhere to a strict diet and control that only the "right" products enter the body;

Take 300 ml of pharmacy chamomile and mint tincture in three equal doses every day;

Drinking blackberry tea - 50 ml cold four times a day;

In case of intensification of pain in the stomach, you can drink a teaspoon of ordinary vegetable oil (the optimal option is olive oil) every 30 minutes during the day.

Please note: alcohol should be avoided for stomach pain of varying intensity, although many patients report that drinking alcohol is a good sedative. There may be some relief, but this will be a very short-term effect, and the result of such a disorder is difficult to predict at all - alcohol has a destructive effect on the mucous membrane of the stomach.

If the stomach pain is repeated very often, and each time more pain medication is needed to relieve the syndrome, then it is necessary to see a doctor as soon as possible - this is only a symptom lum is characteristic of serious pathologies.

CONCLUSION

STOMACH PAIN REQUIRING EMERGENCY MEDICAL ASSISTANCE

Stomach pain Usually, patients try to fight on their own when stomach hurts, and in some cases, their actions are really beneficial. But there are a number of pathologies that require immediate intervention by healthcare workers. One of them is wound perforation — a rupture of the cavity wall at the site of an existing wound surface. This condition is accompanied by the following symptoms:

Stomach pain - sharp, "dagger", sudden. The intensity of the syndrome is such that the patient lies on his back with his legs tightly pulled to his stomach.

Acute general weakness — in some cases, the patient may experience confusion and even fainting. Increased sweating - the patient's forehead is covered with cold sticky sweat, sweat may also appear on the palms. A sharp decrease in arterial blood pressure and a decrease in pulse rate are caused by internal bleeding. Stomach pain does not bring joy, in most cases it has a throbbing, "tiring" character and appears completely by itself. You should not be afraid of pain, you just need to contact a specialist for help - after determining the cause of this condition, the doctor will prescribe effective and competent treatment.

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